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Towards the Systematic Cross-Civilizational Comparison: How Civilizations Work Case 2: The Indic Civilization

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Building on Liah Greenfeld's (2024) framework of Systematic Cross-Civilizational Comparison, as outlined in her Spring 2024 *CCR* essay, this paper examines the cultural realities of the Indic civilization. Civilizations differ at both the individual level, including cognitive aspects (the structure and content of thought), moral dimensions (values and principles guiding behavior), and emotional patterns (typical emotional responses); and the societal level, i.e., distinct institutions, institutional systems, and historical trajectories (Greenfeld 2024).

In each civilization, these modal dimensions stem from and are shaped by the first civilizational principles — the foundational ideas framing the reality unique to that civilization. In Indic civilization, these principles form a worldview distinct from Chinese and Western civilization, codified in the indigenous languages — Prakrit, Sanskrit, or Pali — and articulated through ancient philosophical texts including the Vedas, Upanishads, the epics Mahabharata, Ramayana, and the Holy Book Gita. As these principles were formulated, they not only defined the Indic civilization's image of reality but in turn also shaped its linguistic reality. Through the transmission of these principles via language, Indic civilization orients the minds of its members, opening them to particular possibilities.

This transmission occurs through neural conditioning, as the use of language imprints the civilizational worldview onto the brains of its users. Indic civilization's first principles, *Rta*, *Dharma*, and *Karma*, influence its cognitive, moral, and emotional frameworks, distinguishing it from other civilizations. This paper traces the Indic civilization from its first principles through its characteristic modes of thought, concepts and values, psychological dynamics, and historical trajectories. The article concludes that the distinction between first principles and different modes of thinking has led to cultural distinctions often overlooked by Western scholars. It emphasizes that comparing civilizations requires a contextually informed and culturally sensitive approach, which academia frequently neglects.

1. What is Civilization, and how does it work?

“A civilization is a distinct, self-enclosed, self-sufficient, and self-generating variant of cultural reality, that — for all intents and purposes independently of other such variants with which it may coexist — has developed over generations, multiplying in the process its interlacing traditions. It is an enduring, self-sufficient culture, with codified first principles, resistant to outside influences; mega- or meta-culture; mega- or meta-tradition, allowing for the existence of numerous specific cultures and traditions within the same set of first principles” (Greenfeld, 2025).

This definition of civilization broadens the understanding of the concept, emphasizing its inherent self-sufficiency and its capacity to operate independently of external cultural influences. It is a system that generates and sustains its own cultural processes, often spanning centuries or even millennia. Civilizations are not static; they evolve and multiply their traditions, but they do so within the boundaries of their own first principles, which remain resistant to outside forces. This enduring independence distinguishes civilizations from other forms of cultural organization, such as nations or religions, which may be more transient or interconnected with external systems.

As Greenfeld (2025) points out, there are three layers of cultural process on the collective level - layers of social institutions, of functionally related systems of institutions (such as religions and nations), and of civilizations. Social institutions are “established way of thinking” as defined by Durkheim (Woods et al., 2020), such as economy, family relations, politics; functionally integrated systems of institutions on the second level in the case of nations are also geopolitically bound systems. Among all other cultural processes on the collective level, civilizations are the most distinct due to their foundational independence, which explains their durability and causal sway, making them also the most significant or influential.

Civilizations are family sets of autonomous systems united by shared first principles. These principles, exemplified by notions like monotheism and logic of the monotheistic civilization, serve as the bedrock ideologies shaping a civilization's collective consciousness. Civilizations, in contrast to other layers of the cultural process on the collective level, possess the unique quality of mutual cultural independence. While religions, nations, and institutions within particular spheres are autonomous but not independent from other functionally integrated systems within the same civilization or other institutions within the same functionally integrated system, civilizations stand apart from other civilizations as independent entities that unite diverse autonomous traditions into cultural families while distinguishing them from other cultural families.

Autonomous systems within civilizations share common first principles and evolve interdependently, though without systematic connection to one another.

According to Durkheim and Mauss (1913), civilizations form the supra-national sphere of social life, distinct from the other cultural processes, these are social phenomena which, in their parlance, do not strictly correspond to a specific social organism, they extend over areas which transcend national territories and/or develop over periods which transcend histories of any single society.

Civilization works through conditioning the mind, the essential cultural process on the individual level. The ‘first principles’ (which refers to binding, unquestioned values and ideas), when codified in the written language itself, formed in the process of this codification, give rise to, and through language maintain modes of thought that, together with the said binding values and ideas, determine existential experience.

In turn, the modes of thought generated on the basis of first principles, codified in written language, influence the human mind and give rise to abstract concepts, which define cultural norms, ethical codes, and societal values. These abstract concepts and values create a mold for judgment and inferences in the form of philosophical writing, in literature that dictate how individuals perceive the world, interpret reality, and define their values, creating a framework that echoes across generations. These day-to-day norms and practices, deeply rooted in the civilization's inherent principles, create a self-contained system that often stands completely apart from other civilizations. This self-sufficiency, stemming from the civilization's intrinsic norms and beliefs, renders it resilient to external influences and resistant to swift or substantial changes, thereby maintaining its distinct identity and character over time.

In the case of Indian civilization, the foundational principles *Rta*, *Dharma*, and *Karma* have significantly influenced the societal structures and cultural framing of the Indic mind. These concepts are integral to Indian societal frameworks, with the idea of cosmic justice at the core, from which derive the importance of ethical conduct and moral responsibility. During millennia, these principles have been transmitted both orally and in texts. Oral traditions continue from family to family, generation to generation, whereas written forms of the transmission use the Sanskrit language or symbols. In this way, the values and lessons of Hinduism's ancient texts, the Vedas, *the Gita*, and the tales of the Mahabharata and the Ramayana, still underlie the thinking and behavior among Indian masses.

One can observe the ancient first principles in the prominence of spirituality and rituals in contemporary Indian society and in the persistence of the characteristic spiritual quest for understanding existence through attending religious fairs such as kumbh mela, worshiping nature and so on. This attitude forms an essential aspect of today's living experiences and societal functioning. The enduring nature of Indian civilization can be traced through its 5000 years of tradition, demonstrating continuity in everyday practices, philosophical ideas, and artistic expressions that still contribute to the unique fabric of Indian society.

It is this civilizational continuity, this uninterrupted transmission of the first principles at the deep level of consciousness, despite numerous surface changes, that renders India self-sufficient and virtually impenetrable to outside cultural influences, notwithstanding the 1000 years of Muslim rule and two centuries of British colonization.

1.1 Brahman (Paramatma) as a Supreme Soul

At the core of the Indic philosophical framework lies the concept of *Brahman* — the ultimate, all-encompassing reality that transcends space, time, and causation. Unlike monotheistic paradigms, which advocate for an exclusive relationship with a singular divine entity, the Indic civilization celebrates multiple manifestations of divinity, such as Lord Shiva, Lord Vishnu, Lord Indra, Goddess Saraswati, Goddess Durga, yet all are ultimately part of the transcendent reality of *Brahman*. As Rig Veda verse 1.164.46¹ says “*Indram Mitram Varunam Agnim aahur atho divyaha sa suparno garutmaan, Ekam Sad vipraah bahudhaa vadanti agnim yamam Matarishvaanam aahu*”. [Meaning: They call Him Indra/King of heavens, Mitra/the sun-God, Varuna/the regent of the ocean, Agni/the fire god, Yama/God of death, Maatarishvaan/wind-god, and He is the beautiful winged heavenly Garuda bird. The Truth is one but the wise describe it variously.]

The Supreme Reality is one without a second.

It is the creator of the entire universe; the fourteen worlds², and also, transcends it. This Absolute Reality/God is above Existence and Non-Existence; above Cause and Effect.

It is above space, time and causation.

Bhagavat Gita, chapter 15 verse 17, mentions that “*uttamah puruṣhas tv anyah paramātmety udāhṛtaḥ yo loka-trayam āviśhya bibharty avyaya īśhvaraḥ*” translated as “Besides these, is the supreme divine personality, who is the indestructible supreme soul (Mukundananda, n.d.-c). He enters the three worlds as the unchanging controller and supports all living beings”. Lord Krishna in these verses introduces the concept of God as the supreme divine personality, known as *Paramātma* (Param meaning Supreme, Atma implies soul), or the supreme soul. While *Paramātmā* denotes the ultimate, transcendental reality, *ātmā*, represents the individual soul.

¹ www.wisdomlib.org. (2021, August 27). *Rig Veda 1.164.46 [English translation]*. <https://www.wisdomlib.org/hinduism/book/rig-veda-english-translation/d/doc830789.html>

² The fourteen lokas or worlds are generally called as *Caturdaśa-bhuvanas*. Of these, six lokas (worlds) are above the earth (Bhuloka) and seven below it. The universe is divided into fourteen planetary systems. Seven planetary systems, called Bhūr, Bhuvar, Svar, Mahar, Janas, Tapas and Satya, are upward planetary systems, one above the other. There are also seven planetary systems downward, known as Atala, Vitala, Sutala, Talātala, Mahātala, Rasātala and Pātāla, gradually, one below the other. See <https://www.iskcon-truth.com/bhu-mandala/fourteen-worlds.html>

Image Description: Showing 14 Lokas (Worlds) as per Hindu beliefs

Source: <https://shorturl.at/FSGr6>

Paramātmā governs both the material and spiritual realms, standing apart from the individual soul. While the individual soul is limited in scope, confined to the physical body it inhabits, the Supreme Soul is infinite and resides within every living being. Paramātmā serves as the eternal companion of the individual soul across lifetimes, regardless of the species into which the soul is born.

Lord Krishna himself says in Gita chapter 5 verses 18 “*vidyā-vinaya-sampanne brāhmaṇe gavi hastini, śhuni chaiva śhva-pāke cha paṇḍitāḥ sama-darśinaḥ*” meaning “The truly learned, with the eyes of divine knowledge, see with equal vision a Brahmin, a cow, an elephant, a dog, and a dog-eater” (EternalReligion.org, n.d.). Here, Shree Krishna illustrates starkly different life forms: a Vedic Brahmin, revered for performing rituals; a dog-eater, often stigmatized as an outcaste; a cow, valued for its milk; a dog, viewed differently in societal contexts; and an elephant, celebrated in ceremonial parades. While these beings differ vastly in their societal roles and treatment, the *Bhagavad-Gita* transcends distinctions of race, origin, color, religion, community, or class. It teaches that all beings are eternal souls, inseparable from the Supreme Divine. A truly enlightened individual, endowed with this spiritual understanding, perceives all living entities as equal and eternal souls, inseparable from the Supreme Divine.

Mukundananda (n.d), a scholar of Hindu studies in his commentary of Gita comments that “if a soul takes birth in the form of a dog, the Supreme Soul remains present within, ensuring outcomes aligned with the soul’s accumulated karmas.

He said this is the reason why the lives of dogs differ so significantly — some live in comfort as cherished pets, while others struggle on the streets. Such variations are rooted in the karmic accounts carried over from previous lives, and Paramātmā continues to oversee and balance these accounts across births.”³

In another verses of Gita: chapter 4.24 says “*brahmārpaṇam brahma havir brahmāgnau brahmaṇā hutam, brahmaiva tena gantavyam brahma-karma-samādhinā*” [Meaning: For those who are completely absorbed in God-consciousness, the oblation is Brahman, the ladle with which it is offered is Brahman, the act of offering is Brahman, and the sacrificial fire is also Brahman. Such persons, who view everything as God, easily attain Him.”⁴] The devotee who understands the oneness of God, the Self, and the Universe rises above malice towards all beings. Letting go of notions of "I" and "Mine," they cultivate friendliness, compassion, and contentment in life. They maintain equanimity in both joy and sorrow, avoiding being a source of trouble to others or feeling disturbed by them. Free from fear and agitation, they remain ever satisfied, detached, and impartial, rising above distractions and the confines of ego. Since ego is the root of all suffering, overcoming it leads the devotee to eternal bliss.

2. The Foundational Principles: Ṛta, Dharma, Karma

Understanding contemporary Indian social reality requires integrating indigenous social frameworks that reflect the cultural, spiritual, and communal foundations unique to an Indic society. Many mainstream theories from the West often lack the depth to fully capture the reality of Indian social structures, which are deeply influenced by its First Principles i.e., *Ṛta*, *Dharma*, and *Karma* (Doniger 1980; Harle 1998; Sirswal 2011; Das 2018; Dillard 2020). Unlike the Western emphasis on individual autonomy, Indian social thought is inherently relational, rooted in the belief that each person’s identity is defined by their connections to family, community, and larger societal structures.

Who you are is decided by what duties you are performing, and what duties you are performing define which social position you occupy. Are you Dharmic, or are you distracted from the path of Dharma? The nature of your duty, your virtue (relationship to Dharma), are interconnected, and their interconnection defines you, positions you, and creates the social expectations everybody has from you. The concept of *Ṛta* symbolizes this interconnectedness by asserting that the universe operates according to an underlying harmony (Chaturvedi 2016).

³ Mukundananda, Swami. “BG 15.17: Chapter 15, Verse 17 – Bhagavad Gita, the Song of God – Swami Mukundananda.” *Bhagavad Gita - the Song of God*, by Swami Mukundananda, www.holy-bhagavad-gita.org/chapter/15/verse/17 .

⁴ Mukundananda (“BG 4.24: Chapter 4, Verse 24 – Bhagavad Gita, the Song of God – Swami Mukundananda”) <https://www.holy-bhagavad-gita.org/chapter/4/verse/24>

2.1 Rta as a Cosmic Order and Governing Force

The term Rta (ऋत) derived from the root *r*, signifies "proper," "right," or "true," emphasizing moral and cosmic order. It is the natural law governing the way things inherently function in the universe, often referred to as the "thing-in-itself." This includes the revolution of planets, the changing of seasons, and the innate nature of all living beings.⁵ The term also conveys respect, brightness, and movement, as well as being used metaphorically for states of consciousness, such as being "affected by happiness" (*sukhena rtaḥ*).

As an adverb (*rtam*), it means "rightly" or "properly." In its noun forms, Rta encompasses diverse concepts: it represents the sun, sacrifice, divine law, sacred customs, and even water, as in the invocation, "I purify you with truth" (*satyaṃ tvā rtena pariṣiñcāmi*). Additionally, Rta is personified as divine truth or an object of worship, truth in speech (*rtam ca sūnṛtā vāṇī*), livelihood through gleanings, and the fruit of one's actions.⁶ This meaning of Rta emphasizes the inherent distinction between Indic and monotheistic concepts of abstraction. In monotheistic civilizations, each of these categories, such as truth, propriety, divine law, and so on, is treated as separate and distinct. However, in the Indic context, such concepts are not confined to separate categories. Instead, they overlap and interweave, forming one general and all-encompassing category. This, in turn, means that the first principles of Indian civilization in no way encourage thinking based on the logic of no contradiction (what is known as Aristotelian), encouraged by consistent monotheism (Greenfeld 2025). The characteristic Indian mode of thought, thus, is radically different from the mode of thought of the monotheistic civilization, in the West and elsewhere.

In the Rigveda, Rta embodies the principles of harmony and balance both in nature and human society. Here it is portrayed in three dimensions:

1. Cosmic Order: The natural laws that govern the universe.
2. Divine Order: The principles followed by the gods, especially during rituals (*yajnas*).
3. Moral Order: Ethical conduct expected of humans.

Verses 4.23.8 to 4.23.10 of the Rigveda collectively highlight the metaphysical, ethical, and ecological dimensions of Rta, situating it as the foundation of both universal order and individual action (Samarpanananda, 2009). It is stated there that "Living beings and the world of matter participate in a beautiful orderly life through the power of the eternal and sacred law, *rta*, working in and through them":

⁵ www.wisdomlib.org. *Rita, Rta: 23 Definitions*. 17 July 2024, www.wisdomlib.org/definition/rita .

⁶ DDSA: The practical Sanskrit-English dictionary <https://www.wisdomlib.org/definition/rita>

“Rtasya hi śurudhaḥ santi pūrvī- rtasya dhītirvṛjinānī hanti; Rtasya śloko badhirā tatar da karṇā budhānaḥ śucamāna āyoh” (4.23.8).

[Meaning: Indeed, the guardians of ṛta have existed since ancient times. The wisdom of ṛta destroys misdeeds. The proclamation of ṛta has pierced through the deaf, awakening their ears; it enlightens the wise and purifies their life’s path.] This verse highlights the eternal nature of *ṛta* and its transformative power in dispelling ignorance and wrongdoing. In the Vedic tradition, aligning oneself with *Ṛta* is not a passive act but an active pursuit of harmony. The individual’s actions contribute to the sustenance and flourishing of *Ṛta*, reinforcing a reciprocal relationship between human effort and the universe. This dynamic interplay stresses the Vedic ideal that righteousness and truth are not merely external principles but lived realities that shape both individual and collective existence.

(4.23.9) Rtasya dṛḷhā dharuṇāni santi purūṇi candrā vapuṣe vapūṃṣi; Rtena dīrgham-iṣaṇanta pṛkṣa rtena gāva ṛtamā viveśuḥ.

[Meaning: Firm-seated are the eternal law’s foundations; In its fair form there are many splendid beauties. By the holy law long lasting food they bring us; by the holy law have cows come to our worship.] The verses reflect on the unshakable and radiant nature of *Ṛta*, its role in sustaining life and order in the universe, reinforcing its integral connection to both the material and spiritual realms.

(4.23.10) “Rtam yemāna ṛtamid vanoty- rtasya śuṣmasturayā u gavyuḥ; Rṭāya pṛthvī bahule gabhīreṛtāya dhenū paramē duhāte.”

[Meaning - Guided by *ṛta* (cosmic order), one attains *Ṛta* itself, and by *Ṛta*, wealth is acquired. Through the power of *ṛta*, the swift ones (seekers) strive for the cows. For *ṛta*, the vast and deep earth exists; for *ṛta*, the heavenly cows give their milk in the highest realm] (4.23.8-10). The verse emphasizes the firm and radiant nature of *Ṛta*, describing its deep-rooted foundations and its manifestation in various splendid forms. It highlights *Ṛta* as a sustaining force, ensuring abundance and nourishment, symbolized by the provision of long-lasting food and the sacred presence of cows in worship. This reinforces the idea that *Ṛta* is not just a cosmic principle but an active, life-sustaining order that requires recognition and adherence through both contemplation and ritual and daily practice.

Through poetic and symbolic imagery, the Rigveda emphasizes *Ṛta*’s dynamic nature, its accessibility to those who align with it, and its centrality to Vedic rituals and ethics. It affirms the all-encompassing influence of *Ṛta*, portraying it as the guiding principle that sustains wealth, effort, the earth, and the divine abundance symbolized by celestial cows. It highlights *Ṛta* as the foundation of cosmic harmony and prosperity.

Together, these verses articulate a vision of Ṛta as both an objective reality and a subjective ideal. It is the foundation of natural and moral order, the source of abundance and harmony, and the ultimate goal and guide of human endeavor. The hymns emphasize that the realization of Ṛta is contingent upon knowledge, action, and ethical alignment, underscoring its centrality to Vedic thought. Here Ṛta is portrayed as a governing force that regulates natural phenomena and upholds moral values within society. When this equilibrium is disrupted in human life, it results in disorder and suffering. This underlying force ensures the balance and proper functioning of the universe, maintaining stability across all realms (Indian Ethics: Individual and Social, n.d.). It becomes evident why *duty* — the correct performance of the responsibilities of one’s social position — occupies such a central place among Indian social values.

The Nighantu (Vedic glossary) lists six synonyms of Ṛta: *बट्, श्रत्, सत्रा, अद्धा, इत्था, ऋतम्* (*Bat, Shrat, Satra, Addha, Ittha, and Rtam*) (Dharmawiki 2019).

The Nirukta (10.41) associates Ṛta with water,⁷ symbolizing its fluid and life-sustaining nature. Varuṇa, the Vedic god of water and oceans, is regarded as the protector of Ṛta. The connection between Ṛta and water emphasizes its role in sustaining and nurturing life. The verses include in Rigveda such as “*The Sindhus (rivers) follow the Ṛta of Varuṇa.*” (Rigveda 2.28.4) “*The wheel of Ṛta revolves around the sky with twelve spokes*” (Rigveda 1.164.11), refers to the cyclical nature of time (a year) and the interconnectedness of cosmic order (Apte, 1942).

At the very outset of the *Mahābhārata* (Mahabharata), Ugraśravā (Ugrasrava) Sauti invokes the concept of ‘Ṛta’ (Rita) in a sacred utterance: “*Ṛtam ekākṣaram Brahma vyāktāvyaṅgam sanātanam.*” Here, ṛta (rita) is intrinsically linked to the ineffable *Parabrahman* and is also associated with the *Vyāktāvyaṅga Puruṣa* (Puruṣa) and *Prakṛti* (Prakṛiti) in *Sāṃkhya* (Samkhya) philosophy. Within the *Mahābhārata*, Ṛta is presented as an absolute, all-encompassing principle. This profound significance is further emphasized in its identification with the divine essence of Narayana, as expressed in the phrase: *ṛtam nārāyaṇātmakam* — meaning ṛta is the very soul of Nārāyaṇa.⁸

2.1.1 Oversimplification of Ṛta as a Concept

During the British colonial period in India, many Western Indologists studying Indian social and cultural reality have misinterpreted Ṛta as a primordial or mythological rather than a philosophical principle (Gelders & Balagangadhara, 2011; Sanil, 2015; Banerjee, 2022). Orientalists dismissed Vedic philosophy as irrational or primitive, resulting in a Eurocentric bias that overlooked the sophistication of the Ṛta notion.

⁷ Monier-Williams Sanskrit-English Dictionary, 1899

⁸ Mahabharat-Puran Kosh. www.purankosh.in/purankosh/rita-1.

For instance, Max Weber's (1958), analysis of Indian religion and civilization, particularly his inquiry into why industrialization and rationalization did not take root in India as they did in the West, is often hailed as a pioneering sociological endeavor (Thapar, 2018). However, Weber's interpretation suffers from a fundamental misreading of Indic concepts, particularly *Rta*, which leads to a superficial and context-free theorization of Indian religious thought.

Weber's central question — why India did not develop industrial capitalism like the West — presumes that rationalization and industrialization are the natural trajectories of all civilizations. This assumption ignores the fact that Indic traditions operate on different foundational principles. For instance, Chapter 16, verse 12 of the Gita⁹ points-

- Indian philosophy does not separate the material from the spiritual; rather, it integrates economic life within a broader ethical and cosmic order.
- The pursuit of wealth (*artha*) is permissible but must be aligned with *Rta* and *Dharma* to avoid greed and exploitation.
- Society is not seen as something to be mechanized for maximum efficiency but as an extension of cosmic harmony.

By ignoring these nuances, Weber's analysis presents Indian civilization as a passive recipient of irrational religious traditions that allegedly hinder economic progress. If Weber had correctly understood *Rta*, he would have recognized that the Indic worldview does not reject systematic thinking or organization but frames them within a naturalistic order that aligns human action with cosmic balance. Rather than being an obstacle to development, *Rta* provides a foundational principle that ensures that economic and social activities do not become exploitative or disruptive. This contrasts sharply with the Western industrial model, where rationalization often leads to alienation, environmental destruction, and unbridled materialism. Thus, Weber's analysis ultimately amounts to a misinterpretation, as his failure to engage with the concept of *Rta* highlights how Western social science often attempts to interpret non-Western traditions using its own yardsticks, without adequately understanding their internal logic. Any sociological analysis that ignores *Rta* remains incomplete, context-free, and ultimately a vague generalization rather than a true understanding of Indian civilization.

Another compelling example of the Western mind's inability to comprehend *Rta* can be traced from George Orwell's generally appreciative comments on Mahatma Gandhi. Orwell, in his essay "*Reflections on Gandhi*" (*the Orwell Foundation*, 1949), admired Gandhi's integrity but could not reconcile Gandhi's moral philosophy with Western rationalism.

⁹ BG 16.12: Chapter 16, Verse 12 –Retrieved February 25, 2025, from <https://www.holy-bhagavad-gita.org/chapter/16/verse/12>

Orwell viewed Gandhi's adherence to satyagraha (alignment with truth which justified civil disobedience), nonviolence, and self-discipline as otherworldly, impractical, and even anti-human — a perspective deeply rooted in the Western separation of morality from cosmic order.

Orwell writes, "*Gandhi's teachings cannot be squared with the belief that Man is the measure of all things, and that our job is to make life worth living on this earth, which is the only earth we have.*" This view contrasts with Rta, which sees humanity as part of a broader, interconnected cosmic order, where ethical living, as prescribed by universal laws, has a far-reaching impact not only on individuals but on the world around them.

Gandhi's practice of nonviolence, fasting, and self-purification aimed at aligning his actions with the eternal cosmic law, Rta, which he believed governed all moral and natural order. His teaching, therefore, was highly practical. Orwell, however, critiques these actions as "otherworldly," saying that they "make sense only on the assumption that God exists, and that the world of solid objects is an illusion to be escaped from." Here, Orwell's rationalist lens fails to grasp the profound spiritual dimension of Gandhi's philosophy, which is not a rejection of the material world, but a recognition that the material world is governed by higher, unseen forces of order — Rta which can only be accessed through moral discipline, selflessness, and alignment with truth. Or, perhaps we should say, Orwell's Western lens fails to grasp the profound Indian dimension of Gandhi's philosophy, in which truth, morality, spirituality, and so on occupy semantic space not in the least corresponding to the one which concept designated by these words occupy in the Western, and generally monotheistic, civilization.

2.2 Dharma: The Moral Order Rooted in Rta

The word *Dharma* has its origins in the Sanskrit root *dhr-* (to hold or support), which is closely related to the Latin word *firmus* (meaning firm or stable). This connection leads to *Dharma* being understood as "what is established or firm," ultimately signifying law or principle. It is derived from the older Vedic Sanskrit *n-stem dharman-*, which meant "bearer" or "supporter," and in a religious context, it is viewed as an aspect of Rta. In the Rigveda, the word *Dharma* appears as *dhárman-* and covers a range of meanings such as "something established or firm" (like poles or supports). Figuratively, it is interpreted as "sustainer" or "supporter" of the deities, which semantically resembles the Greek term *themis* (meaning "fixed decree, statute, law").

In Rigveda 1.22.18, it is stated: "*Vishnu strides forth, establishing Dharma; he makes firm the heavens and earth.*" This verse underlines Dharma's foundational role in maintaining universal stability.

Vishnu, as the protector of Dharma, upholds the cosmic order, reinforcing the idea that righteousness is essential for the balance of the cosmos. Similarly, Rigveda 3.3.1 says “*Agni, thou art the guardian of Rta, the bearer of sacred offerings, sustaining Dharma.*” This hymn emphasizes Agni’s role as both a physical and metaphysical agent that ensures the perpetuation of Dharma through yajna (sacrificial rituals), further linking Dharma with ritualistic and moral obligations. Another important dimension of Dharma in the Rigveda is its connection to liberation and spiritual ascent. In Rigveda 10.154.4, the concept of Dharma as a means to transcendence is suggested: “*Following Dharma, the seeker attains the eternal abode, the path of the enlightened.*” It suggests that living in accordance with Dharma is not merely a social obligation but a path to higher spiritual realization (Vidyabhaskar & Krishna, 2017).

Rigveda frequently interconnects Dharma with Satya (truth) and Vrata (sacred duty or vow), suggesting a tripartite ethical framework. In Rigveda 5.63.1, it is proclaimed: “*By truth (Satya) and Dharma, Mitra and Varuna sustain the world; by Vrata, the heavens are upheld.*” This verse illustrates that Dharma is not an isolated concept but operates alongside truthfulness (Satya) and committed duty (Vrata). This triad forms the ethical and moral bedrock of Vedic thought, shaping the later development of Hindu, Buddhist, and Jain philosophies.

Later, by the time of Classical Sanskrit and in the *Atharvaveda*, the term *Dharma* had evolved to the form *dhámma-* (धर्म). In the Prakrit and Pali languages, the term is rendered as *dhamma*, and in contemporary Indian languages, it often appears as *Dharma*.

In the 3rd century BCE, Mauryan Emperor Ashoka played a key role in the transmission of the concept of *Dharma* to other cultures (Bhargava, 2022). He translated it into Greek and Aramaic in his inscriptions, including the Kandahar Bilingual Rock Inscription and the Kandahar Greek Edicts. In these, he used the Greek word *eusebeia* (εὐσέβεια), meaning piety, spiritual maturity, or godliness, to represent *Dharma*. In Aramaic, he used the term *qšyṭ* (קִשְׁיֻט), which can be translated as standard, right measure, straight, upright, true, and that Ashoka evidently took to mean truth or rectitude, which emphasizes the moral and ethical aspects of *Dharma* in his rule and governance. Thus, the evolution of the term *Dharma* shows its deep-rooted connection to concepts of law, order, and morality, and its adaptability across cultures as a guiding principle for individual and societal conduct (Vagishwari 2015).

Image description - Ashoka's Edicts. *Source* - <https://scroll.in/article/951118/why-ashoka-the-emperor-of-india-who-inspired-the-symbols-of-new-republic>

Description - Ashoka's Edicts
Source <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:AsokaKandahar.jpg>

Dharma, while central to all Indian philosophical traditions, is interpreted in diverse ways, reflecting the varied metaphysical and ethical frameworks of each school of Indian philosophy.¹⁰ The Sāṃkhya school, with its dualistic metaphysics of Puruṣa (consciousness) and Prakṛti (matter), views Dharma as aligned with the balance of the three guṇas (qualities): sattva (purity), rajas (activity), and tamas (inertia). Right action is that which increases sattva, leading to clarity, wisdom, and ultimately liberation. Yoga philosophy, as expounded by Patañjali in the Yoga Sūtras, sees Dharma as meritorious actions that facilitate the cessation of mental fluctuations (citta-vṛtti-nirodha). In the Vaishnav school of thought, Dharma is closely linked to one's duty in relation to God (particularly Viṣṇu/Kṛṣṇa). Unlike other schools that emphasize personal moral development or self-realization, Vaishnavism sees Dharma as inseparable from Bhakti (devotional service). The Bhāgavata Purāṇa and Bhagavad Gītā emphasize *Parama-Dharma*, the supreme duty of surrendering to *Kṛṣṇa* and serving him with love and devotion. This interpretation of Dharma prioritizes divine grace over ritual actions, arguing that ultimate liberation (or enlightenment – mokṣa) is achieved not through asceticism or intellectual knowledge but through unwavering devotion to God.

The Mīmāṃsā school, particularly the Pūrva Mīmāṃsā of Jaimini, is the most explicit in defining Dharma as “that which leads to the highest common good (śśeyas) and is distinguished by Vedic injunctions.” According to Jaimini, founder of Mimamsa philosophy, Dharma is understood primarily through the Vedas rather than empirical means, making scriptural authority the primary source of ethical knowledge (Junankar, 1982). The Mīmāṃsā tradition posits that Dharma is enacted through Vedic sacrifices (yajña) and rituals, which sustain cosmic order while action (karma) is central to human life, and performing one's prescribed duties according to the Vedic injunctions ensures not only individual prosperity but also the harmony of the universe.

The Nyāya and Vaiśeṣika schools conceptualize Dharma in a metaphysical sense, associating it with merit (puṣṇa) and demerit (pāp), which are responsible for an individual's karmic destiny (Bronkhorst, 2004). Dharma is viewed as an unseen force (adrṣṭa) that governs cosmic justice, determining happiness and suffering in accordance with past actions.

¹⁰ The Vedic philosophy, also known as the Sad-Darshana (six philosophical perspectives), named-Sankhya (the study of matter and spirit), Nyaya (logic), Vaisesika (atomic theory), Yoga (the practice of self-realization), Karma-Mimamsa (the science of covert labor), and Vedanta (the science of God realization) is a collection of philosophical traditions that have their roots in the ancient Indian texts. It aims to comprehend the nature of the self, reality, and life's ultimate purpose. Its importance comes from influencing many facets of Indian culture and ideas and from offering fundamental frameworks for both spiritual and intellectual investigation. See <https://www.nextias.com/blog/six-schools-of-indian-philosophy/>

Praśastapāda, a key Vaiśeṣika philosopher, describes Dharma as a quality of the self (puruṣa), leading to liberation (mokṣha) when cultivated through ethical actions and pure intentions. Unlike Mīmāṃsā, which emphasizes ritual duties, Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika integrates moral responsibility with rational inquiry and metaphysical causality, suggesting that Dharma is inherent to the cosmic order but shaped by individual moral choices. The Vedānta tradition, particularly Advaita Vedānta, reinterprets Dharma in relation to Brahman and Moksha (Srinivasan, & Aithal 2023).

While Dharma provides guidance for righteous living, it does not always offer clear-cut morality. As such, the Dharma of individuals varies significantly based on their caste and societal role. For instance, the Dharma of a Brahmin priest focuses on spiritual knowledge, ritual duties, and non-violence, while the Dharma of a Kshatriya warrior centers on duty, courage, and the protection of the kingdom, even if it requires acts of violence. Similarly, the Dharma of a Vaishya (merchant) emphasizes trade, wealth creation, and ensuring prosperity, while the Dharma of a Shudra (laborer) involves service and support for the higher castes. Each caste has its own distinctive duties that guide both individual behavior and social responsibility, reflecting the diverse ways in which Dharma shapes life and society.¹¹

In the Mahabharata tale, Karna, born to the unmarried Kunti and the Sun God, is raised by a charioteer family and is considered a member of the Suta (low caste) community. Despite his low social position, Karna is determined to learn archery and martial skills. He approaches Dronacharya and Parashurama, the renowned Brahmin teachers, to receive training. Dronacharya refuses to teach him due to his lower caste, but Karna ultimately learns archery from Parashurama, a Brahmin sage. However, Karna's Dharma is questioned when Parashurama curses him for lying about his caste. When Parashurama, unaware of Karna's true heritage, finds out that he is not a Brahmin, he curses Karna, ensuring that Karna would forget the most essential weaponry and skill during the crucial battle of the Kurukshetra war.

Another incident of the Mahabharata concerns Ekalavya, a tribal prince, who wanted to learn archery from Dronacharya but was rejected because he was not a Kshatriya. Determined, he created a clay idol of Dronacharya and self-trained, eventually surpassing even Arjuna in skill. When Dronacharya learned of Ekalavya's abilities, he feared that his status as a teacher of the greatest warrior (Arjuna) would be challenged. To uphold Arjuna's superiority, he asked Ekalavya for guru-Dakshina (teacher's offering). Ekalavya, out of devotion, agreed to give anything. Dronacharya then demanded his right thumb, knowing that this would ruin his ability to use a bow. Without hesitation, Ekalavya cut off his thumb, sacrificing his future as an archer.

¹¹ Kindly refer to Rigveda 10.90, the Purusha Sukta hymn "When they divided Purusha, into how many parts did they divide him? What did his mouth become? What his two arms? What are his two thighs and his two feet?" <https://sites.google.com/view/sanatan-dharma/rg-veda-10-90-purusha-sukta>

“In Chapter 18, Verse 47 of the Bhagavad Gita, it is stated: “*It is better to perform one’s own Dharma, even imperfectly, than to perfectly execute another’s Dharma. By adhering to one’s inherent duties, a person avoids incurring sin.*” Mukunda, in his commentary on the Gita, interprets this verse as emphasizing the importance of staying true to one’s natural responsibilities. He explains that each individual is born with a specific role and set of duties aligned with their inherent nature (*swabhava*). Attempting to adopt another’s duties, no matter how skillfully performed, creates disharmony and leads to spiritual and karmic imbalance. Conversely, even if one’s own duties are performed imperfectly, they remain more conducive to personal growth and ethical living, as they are in harmony with one’s true self. For such individuals, Lord Krishna’s ultimate instruction in the Bhagavad Gita (18.66) applies: “Abandon all varieties of duties and surrender unto Me.” However, until this level of spiritual maturity is attained, the Śhrīmad Bhāgavatam (11.20.9) advises continuing prescribed duties until a genuine inclination for devotion — through hearing, chanting, and meditating on God’s divine acts — manifests. This ensures a harmonious progression toward spiritual fulfillment.”¹²

Thus, the tale of Mahabharata was/is more than just an epic tale that deals with the struggles of following one's Dharma. Many characters find themselves at a crossroads, grappling with inner conflicts and the consequences of their choices. The epic reveals that upholding Dharma is rarely easy and often demands great sacrifice. At the same time, it warns that straying from Dharma, whether intentionally or unknowingly, leads to *adharma*, resulting in chaos and suffering. Through its characters' dilemmas, the Mahabharata challenges us to question the true nature of duty and whether the right path is ever truly clear.

Yudhishtira, the eldest brother of Pandavas, renowned for his wisdom and sense of justice, earns the title "*lord of Dharma*". His greatest moment of inner conflict arises after the Kurukshetra War, a devastating battle between the Pandavas (Yudhishtira and his brothers) and the Kauravas — both branches of the Kuru dynasty. Witnessing the immense loss of life, including that of his own relatives, Yudhishtira becomes overwhelmed with grief and contemplates renouncing his throne to live as an ascetic in the forest. However, his advisors, especially Krishna, remind him that while renunciation may be the right path for some, his Dharma as a king is to lead and serve his people. Ultimately, Yudhishtira must reconcile his personal sorrow with his greater duty, illustrating the complexities of Dharma in the epic. Yudhishtira’s most significant challenge occurs during the infamous game of dice, where he gambles away his kingdom, his brothers, and even himself. As a result, he was forced into exile.

¹² “It is better to do one’s own *dharma*, even though imperfectly, than to do another’s *dharma*, even though perfectly. By doing one’s innate duties, a person does not incur sin” <https://www.holy-bhagavad-gita.org/chapter/18/verse/47>

While gambling is against Dharma, his sense of honor and the pressure to abide by the rules of the game, as set by Shakuni and his Kauravas cousins, lead him to make disastrous decisions.

In the battle of Kurukshetra Arjuna's greatest challenge comes when he is on the verge of battle against his own relatives, teachers, and friends. Torn by sorrow and compassion, he hesitates to fight, asking Krishna whether it is righteous to kill his kin for the sake of victory. This moment of doubt represents a conflict between his duty as a Kshatriya (warrior) to fight for justice and his love for his family. "Krishna tells Arjuna that the first thing one must do is to understand his *Dharma* – duty or ethics. The next step is to wage a battle, if needed, 'for the sake of Dharma.'" Krishna wants Arjuna to know that being a warrior, Arjuna can never find a 'greater' purpose than to partake in *dharmayuddha*, (a righteous war). Krishna instructs Arjuna that the first and foremost duty of an individual is to understand his Dharma — his responsibility and moral obligation. He emphasizes that, when necessary, one must fight to uphold Dharma, even if it means engaging in battle. As a Kshatriya, Arjuna's highest duty is to participate in a *dharmayuddha*. Gita Chapter 2 Verse 37"¹³ states, "If you are killed, you shall reach heaven; or if you triumph, you shall enjoy the earth; so, stand up, Son of Kunti, firm in your resolve, to fight!". Contrary to Arjuna's initial hesitation, Krishna explains that avoiding battle would be the real adharmas, as it would mean abandoning his duty when called upon to defend righteousness. He urges Arjuna to rise above his doubts and see beyond the temporary pain of war, which stems from his limited understanding of the world and reality.

Thus, one's Dharma conveys a universal message about duty, righteousness, and the importance of rising above personal dilemmas to fulfill one's moral obligations. It encourages a detached and selfless approach to duty, emphasizing that true justice lies in upholding righteousness rather than being swayed by emotions.

2.3 Dharma in Action as Karma

The principle of Karma, often translated as "action" or "deed," is the mechanism through which Dharma operates in the lives of individuals. Karma is the law of cause and effect, which dictates that every action, whether physical, mental, or verbal, produces consequences that shape an individual's future. Good actions lead to positive outcomes, while bad actions result in suffering and negative consequences. Thus, Karma could be summarized as a moral law that ensures justice and accountability in the universe.

¹³ (The Bhagavad Gita and the Ethics of War - Religion and Humanitarian Principles, 2022).
<https://blogs.icrc.org/religion-humanitarianprinciples/bhagavad-gita-ethics-war>

The word Karma is derived from the Sanskrit root "kr" (कृ), which signifies "to do," "to make," or "to perform." The suffix "-man" (मन्) is added to form the noun *Karman* (कर्मन्), which translates to "action" or "deed."¹⁴ In its most basic sense, Karma refers to any intentional or volitional act, whether physical, verbal, or mental. As per Vedic belief, Karma is not limited to the act itself but also encompasses the consequences or "fruits" (phala) of those actions, which shape an individual's destiny across lifetimes. In the Dharmashastra texts, which codify Hindu law and ethics, Karma is closely linked to the performance of one's prescribed duties (sva-Dharma). For instance, the Manu smṛiti outlines the six primary duties (karmas) of a Brahmin:

1. Adhyāpana (अध्यापन): teaching.
2. Adhyayana (अध्ययन): studying.
3. Yajana (यजन): performing sacrifices for oneself.
4. Yājana (याजन): performing sacrifices for others.
5. Dāna (दान): giving gifts.
6. Pratigraha (प्रतिग्रह): receiving gifts.

These duties are not arbitrary but are aligned with the Ṛta and the individual's role in maintaining social and spiritual harmony. The performance of these duties generates positive Karma, which contributes to the individual's spiritual progress and the well-being of society.

In the Śivapurāṇa (1.18)¹⁵, the concept of Karma (कर्म) is intricately linked to the activities of the body (*śhārira*) and the cyclical nature of birth, death, and rebirth. The text elucidates that the body and Karma are mutually dependent: the body performs actions, and these actions, in turn, generate the conditions for future births, creating an endless cycle likened to a revolving wheel (chakra) (Śivapurāṇa 1.18). The Śivapurāṇa categorizes the body into three types, each playing a distinct role in the experience of Karma:

1. *Sthūla śhārira*: The gross physical body, which is responsible for all physical activities (karma).
2. *Sūkṣma śhārira* : The subtle body, which facilitates the enjoyment of sensory pleasures.
3. *Kāraṇa śhārira* : The causal body, which stores the impressions of past actions and determines the experiences of happiness or suffering based on virtuous or sinful deeds (Śivapurāṇa 1.18).

¹⁴ Etymology of Karma. Please See <https://www.wisdomlib.org/definition/karma>

¹⁵ Archive.org: Shiva Purana - English Translation

The *Jīva* (individual soul) is bound by the "rope of Karma" (*karmarajju*), which ties it to the cycle of *saṃsāra*. Virtuous actions lead to happiness, while sinful actions result in misery, perpetuating the soul's journey through repeated births and deaths (Śivapurāṇa 1.18). This framework stresses the ethical and spiritual dimensions of Karma, emphasizing its role as a driving force in the cosmic order and the individual's path toward liberation (moksha).

In Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika philosophy¹⁶, Karma is an independent category inherent in substances but distinct from qualities. Kaṇāda classifies Karma into five types: *utkṣepaṇa* (upward motion), *avakṣepaṇa* (downward motion), *ākuñcana* (contraction), *prasāraṇa* (expansion), and *gamana* (locomotion). In Shaiva philosophy, particularly in Kashmir Śaivism, Karma is regarded as "the door to knowledge" (*Cittānubodhaśāstra*). Here, action is not just a means of worldly engagement but a crucial step toward self-realization and divine recognition (*Pratyabhijñā*).

According to Vedānta, Karma functions through the law of cause and effect, where every action yields corresponding results (Potter 1980). It is classified into *sañcita* (accumulated past actions), *prārabdha* (presently unfolding actions), and *kriyamāṇa* (ongoing or future actions). Good deeds (*puṇya-karma*) lead to spiritual upliftment, while negative actions (*pāpa-karma*) result in suffering. This doctrine reinforces the idea that one's present circumstances are shaped by past actions, and future outcomes are determined by present choices. In Shaivism, Karma is intrinsically linked to spiritual awakening, where the realization of the true nature of the self transcends the cycle of actions and their consequences. Thus, Karma, beyond being a mere cause-and-effect mechanism, serves as a pathway to higher wisdom and liberation in Śaiva thought.

Gita chapter 2 verse 47 emphasizes that karma refers to selfless action performed without attachment to results, guided by duty (*Dharma*) and moral principles.¹⁷ It says, "You have a right to perform your prescribed duties, but you are not entitled to the fruits of your actions. Never consider yourself to be the cause of the results of your activities, nor be attached to inaction". This understanding of karma promotes a balanced, ethical, and purposeful approach to life.

3. Interlinking Rta, Dharma, Karma

The concept of Rta establishes a foundational cosmic order, ensuring the universe's stability and ethical structure.

¹⁶ Please refer to Shodhganga: A study of Nyāya-vaiśeṣika categories.

¹⁷ The concept of karma in the Bhagavad. (n.d.)

<https://www.wabashcenter.wabash.edu/syllabi/w/wattles/hkarma.html>

However, in the realm of human conduct, this cosmic principle manifests as *Dharma* — the moral and social duty that sustains individual and collective well-being. While *Ṛta* governs the universe as an inherent law, *Dharma* represents the conscious adherence to that law through righteous action. Kiron Krishnan (2020) explains that *Ṛta* is intrinsically linked to the concept of *Dharma*. While *Dharma* represents "rightness" or the ethical duties one ought to perform, *Ṛta* is the underlying principle that makes *Dharma* valid and meaningful. In essence, *Dharma* is what one should do, and *Ṛta* is why one should do it. *Ṛta* embodies the natural order and tendencies within the cosmos that sustain equilibrium, regularity, and sustainable patterns of existence, as opposed to chaos and dissolution (*Ṛta, Satya, Dharma: The Interconnectedness in Meaning*, n.d). It is the rule of how things should be, ensuring harmony and adherence. Further, *yagnya* (sacrifice or ritual) is a traditional means of aligning with *Ṛta*, as it promotes and is promoted by this cosmic order, serving as a bridge between human actions and universal harmony.

As Indologist Ganesh and Ravikumar (2015) write: “In Rigveda and Atharvaveda, the law behind existence is *Ṛta*, and to tamper with it will prove deadly. The whole of creation is called *sat*, which has an inbuilt cosmic law, *Ṛta*. If *sat* (truth/existence) is a fact, then the value that we realize out of it is *Ṛta*. When we realize *Ṛta*, the value of the whole of creation, we are humbled and naturally become more caring towards the universe. The entire universe supports our sustenance and the whole of creation toils for our existence.

Dharma also functions as the lived expression of *ṛta*, translating cosmic balance into human ethics. The Mahābhārata (12.110.11) encapsulates this relationship: (*Dhāraṇāddharmamityāhuḥ dharmo dhārayate prajāḥ.*) “*Dharma is so called because it upholds; Dharma sustains all beings.*” This verse stresses the fundamental role of *Dharma* in maintaining order, not only within the cosmos but also in human society. The individual’s duty (*svadharma*) aligns with the larger moral framework of the world, ensuring that social structures function in harmony with the cosmic order. In this view, a person’s responsibilities as a parent, student, worker, or elder are distinct and carry specific moral expectations. For example, within a family, the head of the household has a duty to provide, protect, and guide, while younger members are expected to respect and support the family unit. This creates a layered and communal approach to ethics, where obligations are collective rather than individual, reinforcing social cohesion and mutual dependency. Prioritizing *Dharma* within social analysis allows for a more culturally accurate view of Indian society, where communal roles are fundamental to identity formation and ethical behavior (Holdrege 2004). Just as *ṛta* ensures the movement of celestial bodies, *Dharma* dictates the rightful actions of individuals in accordance with their position in life.

A disruption in *Rta* results in cosmic disorder; similarly, the neglect of *Dharma* leads to societal and moral decay. Thus, the *Bhagavad Gita* (7.3) states that “*Amongst thousands of persons, hardly one strives for perfection; and amongst those who have achieved perfection, hardly one knows Me in truth.*” This emphasizes the rarity of true spiritual perfection and highlights the human tendency to focus on materialistic pursuits, such as eating, sleeping, reproduction, and defense, which are shared with animals. While these basic instincts are part of human nature, the true distinction of humans rests in their ability to transcend these desires and align with higher spiritual truths.

This verse suggests that despite material advancements, such as technology or societal progress, without the pursuit of spiritual *Dharma*, these achievements remain insignificant in the grand scheme of the universe.¹⁸ The comparison between human behavior and that of animals underscores the critique of defining civilization¹⁹ merely by material success, rather than by spiritual knowledge and ethical alignment with *Rta*. It alludes to the importance of intention in one’s actions, emphasizing that the true path to perfection is not only through righteous deeds but through understanding and embodying the spiritual truths behind them (Prabhupada, 1975).

The *Bhagavad Gītā* (4.7-4.8) also reflects on interconnectedness, where Krishna proclaims that whenever *Dharma* declines and *adharma* (unrighteousness) prevails, divine intervention restores balance. This cyclical restoration mirrors the Vedic understanding of *Rta*, reinforcing the idea that the universe and human society function through a delicate yet enduring equilibrium (Das, 2018).

Among other mythological stories in Hinduism, the Jataka tales²⁰ provide a profound exploration of *Rta* and *Dharma*, revealing how these concepts differ significantly from Western understandings, among other things, due to the distinct modes of thought they generate. It demonstrates the selflessness and moral duty inherent in *Dharma*, providing a lens through which to understand how living in harmony with *Rta* is a central aspect of Indic civilization, distinct from the mundane, individualistic, and outcome-driven approaches characteristic of the West. The story says, “*Born into a family of Brahmans renowned for their purity of conduct and great spiritual devotion, the bodhisattva became a great scholar and teacher. With no desire for wealth and gain, he entered a forest retreat and began a life as an ascetic. It was in this forest that he encountered a tigress who was starving and emaciated from giving birth and was about to resort to eating her own newborn cubs for survival.*”

¹⁸ Prabhupada, A. B. S.-. S. (n.d.). *Bhagavad-Gītā As it is* 7.3. Vedabase. <https://vedabase.io/en/library/bg/7/3/>

¹⁹ Here Civilization has been used in a civilized context.

²⁰ “A voluminous body of literature native to the Indian subcontinent which mainly concern the previous births of Gautama Buddha in both human and animal form” https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Jataka_tales#cite_note-:1-1

*With no food in sight, the bodhisattva, out of infinite compassion, offered his body as food to the tigress, selflessly forfeiting his own life”.*²¹

The prince’s self-sacrifice aligns with Rta because it is an act of Dharma, where the prince recognizes that his life is not separate from the lives of other beings. Sacrifice for the welfare of others, especially in times of need, is a moral duty embedded in the cosmic order. This concept stands in contrast to Western stress on the unique, both finite and irreproducible, individual, where personal rights and survival are often prioritized over collective well-being and self-sacrifice, and always prioritized over *eternal* cosmic order. The prince's decision to offer himself up as nourishment for the tiger is an eloquent reflection of the ethical dimension of Rta, which goes beyond limited rational calculation or legalism, focusing on the welfare of the universe and all its beings.

This ethical ideal would be difficult for a Western perspective to fully appreciate, as it goes against the notion of self-preservation that dominates much of Western philosophy, and, which is equally important, the Western idea of time. This story reinforces the idea of interdependence within the cosmic order. In Indian thought, all beings — humans, animals, plants, and even the earth — are seen as interconnected through the principle of Rta. The prince's sacrifice is not seen as a futile or irrational act, but rather as a fulfillment of Dharma, maintaining the balance of the universe. This understanding of universal interconnection contrasts with the Western view of separate, isolated individuals (human or animal) (or each category) with their special interests and rights.

Image Description: Based on understanding of Greenfeld CCR essay (2024), made by author.

²¹ https://www.reddit.com/r/Buddhism/comments/7qcke1/story_of_the_starving_tigress_is_this_story/?rdt=53694

4. Deconstructing Western Misunderstandings

4.1 Dharma: Questioning Universalism

Civilizations endure not merely through the passage of time but through their ability to renew and revitalize themselves in the face of deterioration. Throughout history, cultures have undergone phases of renewal — what is often termed revival in a religious context and renaissance in a cultural one. The Indic civilization, with its deep philosophical traditions, has witnessed numerous such renaissances, yet these remain largely unrecognized in dominant academic and global narratives. While cultures of Western civilization proudly document their own intellectual and cultural revivals, Western scholars often overlook the recurring cycles of renewal that have sustained Indic civilization for millennia. Among natives, there is always an urge to restore the authenticity and intellectual autonomy of Indic traditions, misunderstood or reinterpreted by external agents. They wish to assert, reclaim, and celebrate the unique philosophical, cultural, and spiritual heritage of Indic civilization, free from external distortions or dominance.

A central aspect of this is to focus on Dharma in Indic civilization, which is often misunderstood or marginalized by Western frameworks of universalism. Universalist paradigms, with their emphasis on homogenization, tend to impose external standards on non-Western traditions, leading to a profound misrepresentation of Dharma's essence. William Archer's book *India and the Future*, published in 1917, while possibly intended to enlighten the Western world about Indian culture, presented a distorted concept and principles of Indic civilization with a Western yardstick. Full of colonial hubris and little else, Archer made numerous misguided assertions about Hinduism, including claims of barbarism and lack of morality (*A Rationalistic Critic on Indian Culture - I*, n.d.). His work, though popular among the English aristocracy for its exoticism and confirmation of their preconceived notions, was heavily criticized by prominent Indian scholars, such as Sri Aurobindo Ghosh. In defense of Indian culture, Ghosh critiques Archer's book as not a genuine work of scholarship, but rather a form of literary or journalistic aggression (*A Critic of Mr Archer on Indian Culture*, 2004). He argues that Archer's is a reckless attack on a simplified, distorted version of India, driven by a desire to impress an uninformed audience with exaggerated misstatements and unfounded claims. Archer's approach lacks balance, fairness, and reason, aiming only to create the illusion of delivering decisive blows. In this pursuit, facts are manipulated, caricatured, and inconsistencies are overlooked if they serve the intended narrative. Ghosh asserts that this is not a momentary lapse from a well-informed scholar but rather a deliberate and irresponsible attempt to strike at a culture from a position of ignorance and bias.

Archer's portrayal of Hinduism as an "unhappy" and "immoral"²² religion ignores its profound philosophical depth, ethical frameworks, such as Dharma and ahimsa, and spiritual practices such as Pranayama, which he reductively describes as "sitting cross-legged and contemplating one's own navel" (Similarly, his characterization of Indian art as "gargantuan excess" and Hindu music as "hopelessly inferior" reveals a lack of appreciation for the intricate craftsmanship, spiritual symbolism, and cultural richness that define these traditions. Archer's superficial interpretations of Hindu deities, such as Rama and Sita, further demonstrate his inability to grasp the complexity of Indian culture.

Indologist and scholar of Hindu studies Rajiv Malhotra, in his work "Being Different" (2011), asserts that the Western lens distorts Dharma by confining it to "religion" in a monotheistic sense, thereby stripping it of its broader cosmic, moral, and societal dimensions. He states, "Western scholars have systematically mapped Hindu Dharma onto their own religious frameworks, ignoring its fluidity and integral relationship with karma, yoga, and self-realization." (Tilak 2012). Rajiv Malhotra critiques Western universalism by contrasting Indic traditions with the Judeo-Christian worldview, particularly in their approach to knowledge, unity, and cultural engagement. He introduces the concept of "embodied knowing," which highlights the Indic tradition's emphasis on inner experience and self-realization, in contrast to the West's history-centrism, which prioritizes religious, cultural, and economic homogenization (Gier 2012). Malhotra differentiates between "integral unity," an inherent oneness found in Dharmic traditions, and "synthetic unity," a pragmatic Western model that unites fundamentally disunited individuals and groups. He argues that synthetic unity fuels internal conflicts within the West and external aggression toward others. Additionally, he explores how Indic traditions embrace chaos as part of cosmic order, whereas the West perceives it as a threat. Malhotra also challenges Western reinterpretations of Sanskrit, particularly by missionaries and secular scholars, who attempt to reshape its meanings to fit their own frameworks. His concluding chapters critique Western universalism and propose *pūrva-pakṣa* (a method of critical engagement with opposing views) as a means to counteract these distortions and reclaim the autonomy of Indic thought.

Similarly, S.N. Balagangadhara, a Ghent scholar, argues that Western academia universalizes its own epistemological categories, leading to incorrect translations and misrepresentations of Dharma. In his work "The Heathen in His Blindness" (1996), he critiques the colonial construction of Indian traditions, stating, "*The West created Hinduism as a 'religion' by imposing its own theological categories on a civilization that had no equivalent concept.*"

²² (William Archer: The Indologist Who Took Shots at Hinduism with Inaccurate Arrows, 2023)

He emphasizes that Dharma is not a rigid set of commandments but a contextual and evolving principle guiding individual and social conduct (Almond 1996).

The critiques and misrepresentations of Indic civilization stem from a fundamental disconnect rooted in the absence of contextual understanding, arising from the inherent differences between Western and Indian civilizational frameworks. The Western intellectual tradition, shaped by the idea of one God and Enlightenment rationalism, often approaches non-Western traditions through a universalist, homogenizing lens, leading to misinterpretations. In contrast, the Indic philosophy emphasizes fluidity, contextual understanding, and integral unity, as seen in concepts like Dharma, karma, and self-realization. To address this gap, Western scholarship must move beyond its context-free analysis and adopt a more contextualized approach, aligning its methodologies with the first principles of that particular civilization. This involves recognizing the limitations of universalist paradigms and embracing pluralistic frameworks that appreciate the unique epistemological and ontological foundations of Indic thought.

4.2 Karma Beyond Moral Punishment

The principles of Karma are closely tied to the idea of Dharma (धर्म), which guides moral duty, righteousness, and the ethical framework that governs human conduct. Just as Rta (ऋत) represents the cosmic order, Dharma translates this universal principle into the realm of human action, providing a guide for righteous living. Karma, in turn, is the mechanism through which Dharma is enacted and its consequences realized. However, in the West, karma is often simplified to the idea of “what goes around comes around” or a universal system of reward and punishment, where good deeds are believed to bring good fortune, and bad deeds lead to the suffering of the agent (Evans, 2024). This interpretation is heavily influenced by Western cultural and religious frameworks, particularly the notion of a divine judge who rewards or punishes based on actions. The Western interpretation of karma as a moral justice system tied to fairness and equality often creates unrealistic expectations, such as believing that good deeds will always be rewarded or that suffering is always a result of past wrongdoings. This mindset can lead to frustration, self-blame, and a focus on external rewards rather than intrinsic moral growth.

The story of Garuda and the Bird serves as a profound illustration of karma and its intricate consequences, challenging the Western tendency to oversimplify it as a system of reward and punishment. In the tale, Garuda, the divine eagle and vehicle of Lord Vishnu, attempts to save a tiny bird from its impending death after it trembles in fear upon seeing Yamaraj, the God of death. Acting out of compassion, Garuda carries the bird far away to a dense forest, believing he has rescued it.

However, Yamaraj later reveals that the bird was destined to die in that very forest by a serpent's bite, and Garuda's intervention unknowingly fulfilled its fate.²³ This paradox highlights a central tenet of Hindu karmic philosophy: the moral weight of an action lies in its intention, not its outcome also mentioned in Bhagavad Gita in 2.47 "*You have a right to perform your prescribed duty, but you are not entitled to the fruits of action. Never consider yourself the cause of the results of your actions, and never be attached to not doing your duty*". Although Garuda's compassionate intention was admirable, the outcome lay beyond his control, demonstrating how karma functions within an intricate network of interconnected actions, intentions, and destinies.

Unlike the Western view of karma as a linear, agent-focused cause-and-effect system, Hindu philosophy emphasizes that individual actions are part of a larger cosmic order, where outcomes are often unpredictable and influenced by past karmas (*prarabdha*). Yamaraj's revelation that the bird was destined to die in the forest illustrates how karma functions within a vast cosmic framework, where individual actions are woven into a greater, often inscrutable, design. The story also stresses the delicate balance between fate and free will, showing that while certain events are predestined, individuals still have the power to act with compassion and mindfulness. Thus, "Garuda and the Bird" story serves as a reminder that life is filled with uncertainties, and even well-intentioned actions can have unintended consequences. By embracing this nuanced understanding of karma, we can move beyond the simplistic notion of "what goes around comes around" and instead focus on living with humility, compassion, and acceptance of life's complexities.

When Weber, (1916) contended that the Hindu emphasis on ritualism, asceticism, and the cyclical nature of life discouraged the rational pursuit of economic goals, which he saw as essential to the spirit of capitalism, he argued that Hinduism, particularly its Vedic texts and caste system, lacked the motivational framework necessary for the development of a capitalist mindset (Ling, 1980). However, this interpretation overlooks the deeper philosophical and ethical dimensions of Hinduism, particularly its teachings on karma and the ultimate aim of moksha (liberation).

²³ One day, Lord Vishnu traveled to Mount Kailash on his divine vehicle, Garuda, a majestic half-man, half-eagle creature. While waiting outside, Garuda admired the beauty of Mount Kailash, including a tiny, playful bird that added to the serene atmosphere. Suddenly, Yamaraj, the god of death, arrived on his buffalo. As Yamaraj dismounted, he glanced at the bird with a slight frown before entering the mountain. The bird, trembling with fear, confided in Garuda that it had seen its death approaching in Yamaraj's gaze. Moved by compassion, Garuda decided to save the bird. He picked it up in his claws and flew miles away, dropping it in a dense forest. Garuda assured the bird it was now safe, far from Yamaraj's reach, and returned to Mount Kailash. When Yamaraj emerged and inquired about the bird, Garuda proudly explained that he had rescued it and taken it far away. Yamaraj, however, smiled and revealed that the bird was destined to die in that very forest by a serpent's bite. He had been puzzled about how the tiny bird would reach such a distant location, but Garuda had unknowingly fulfilled its fate. Read Story here <https://patnaik Sujatap.wordpress.com/2020/05/25/garuda-and-the-bird/>

When examined through the karmic lens, Hinduism's apparent disinterest in material wealth accumulation emerges not as a lack of motivation but as a deliberate ethical and spiritual choice rooted in its worldview.

From a Hindu perspective, human life is transient — a mere blink in the eternal cycle of birth, death, and rebirth (samsara). The ultimate goal of existence is not the accumulation of material wealth but the transcendence of the material world altogether. This is encapsulated in the concept of moksha, the liberation from the cycle of samsara and the merging with the supreme reality. Within this framework, wealth and material possessions are not inherently evil; rather, they are seen as part of one's Dharma. A householder, for instance, is expected to earn wealth, provide for their family, and contribute to society. However, the pursuit of wealth for its own sake, or attachment to material possessions, is considered a distraction from the higher spiritual goal of liberation.

The principle of karma further reinforces this ethical stance. Every action, including economic activities, generates karmic consequences that bind the individual to the cycle of samsara. While ethical and dharmic accumulation of wealth is permissible, excessive attachment to wealth or unethical practices in its pursuit are seen as generating negative karma, which hinders spiritual progress. Thus, Hinduism does not reject wealth outright but places it within a broader ethical and spiritual framework that prioritizes detachment and the pursuit of higher truths.

Weber's analysis fails to account for this layered understanding of wealth and motivation in Hinduism. What he interprets as a lack of motivation for capitalist enterprise can instead be seen as a deliberate rejection of materialism in favor of spiritual liberation. The Hindu emphasis on detachment (vairagya) and the transient nature of material wealth reflects a profound philosophical insight: that the pursuit of material gain, while necessary for worldly life, is ultimately secondary to the quest for moksha. In this sense, Hinduism does not necessarily discourage economic activity but subordinates it to a higher spiritual purpose.

4.3 Purusharthas: Four Goals of Human Life

Purushartha (पुरुषार्थ) is a Sanskrit word formed from *purusha* (पुरुष), meaning "human being," and *artha* (अर्थ), meaning "purpose" or "object." Together, it translates to "the object of human pursuit" or "the aims of human life." In Indian philosophical traditions, Purushartha refers to the four fundamental goals that provide a structured framework for human existence: *Dharma* (righteousness), *Artha* (prosperity), *Kama* (desire), and *Moksha* (liberation) (Mittal, 2024).

- **Dharma:** The foundation of righteousness, encompassing moral values, duties, and ethical conduct that sustain social harmony and universal order.

- *Artha* refers to the pursuit of wealth, career, and resources necessary for a stable and prosperous life. It emphasizes the importance of economic well-being as a means to support oneself and society. Without *Artha*, the pursuit of *Dharma* and *Kama* becomes challenging, as material stability is essential for moral and emotional fulfillment. Classical Hindu texts, such as the *Arthashastra* and *Manusmriti*, emphasize that economic stability is vital for individuals and society, as it provides the resources needed to uphold *Dharma* and facilitate *kama*. However, *artha* must be pursued ethically and within the boundaries of *Dharma* to ensure that it does not lead to greed or moral corruption. As Gita chapter 16 verse says BG 16.12: “One is entitled to keep only as much wealth as is necessary for one’s maintenance (the rest must be given away in charity). If one accumulates more than one’s need, one is a thief in the eyes of God and will be punished for it.”
- *Kama* signifies the enjoyment of life’s pleasures, including love, emotions, and sensory experiences. It encourages the pursuit of happiness and aesthetic enjoyment while staying within the boundaries of *Dharma*. *Kama* reminds us that life is not just about duty and wealth but also about joy and passion. Bhagavad Gita 7.11 states “*O best of the Bharatas, in strong persons, I am their strength devoid of desire and passion. I am sexual activity not conflicting with virtue or scriptural injunctions*”. Here Lord Krishna describes two aspects of His divine presence: strength and regulated sexual activity. He explains that in strong individuals, He is the serene and virtuous strength free from desire, passion, and attachment. This strength enables them to fulfill their duties responsibly. Regarding sexual activity, Krishna distinguishes between animalistic behavior driven solely by sensual pleasure and virtuous conduct aligned with scriptural principles. He states that he is present in the controlled, virtuous, and purposeful sexual activity within marriage, particularly when it is intended for procreation and adheres to *Dharma* (righteousness).
- *Moksha* represents the highest goal of human life — liberation from the cycle of birth and death. It is the pursuit of self-realization (meaning *the return of the individual soul to Brahman*), freedom, and spiritual awakening. While *Dharma*, *Artha*, and *Kama* focus on worldly life, *Moksha* transcends them, guiding individuals toward eternal peace and enlightenment.

These goals are interdependent, guiding individuals toward a balanced and meaningful life, with *moksha* as the ultimate aim that integrates and transcends the other three (shown in the image below). As stressed in Gita, the ultimate goal of human life is *moksha*, or liberation from bondage. Bondage arises from the ego-centric mindset of “I” and “mine,” which leads to worry, misery, lack of peace, and a sense of inadequacy or failure. This state of bondage, perpetuated across lifetimes, stems from ignorance (*ajnana*). Through the study of Vedanta and deep reflection on its teachings, one can dispel this ignorance, transcend delusion, and attain liberation (*moksha*). In this liberated state, the individual experiences eternal bliss, free from all suffering.

Some believe that performing rituals can lead to moksha. Often, priests conclude rituals by listing the benefits, such as wealth, progeny, honors, and finally, moksha. However, this approach treats moksha as just another reward, rather than the ultimate spiritual goal. Others think that performing holy deeds can grant access to heavenly realms like Vaikuntha or Kailasa, where one can enjoy sensory pleasures or even assume forms similar to the divine. However, these experiences — *Salokata* (living in the Lord's world), *Sameepita* (living near the deity), and *Sarooputa* (assuming the deity's form) — are temporary. Once the merit of the good deeds is exhausted, the individual is cast out of heaven. These states, therefore, do not constitute true moksha. Only Sayujya Mukti, or merging with the Divine, represents genuine liberation.

As Gita 18.51-53 asserts: “One becomes fit to attain Brahman when he or she possesses a purified intellect and firmly restrains the senses, abandoning sound and other objects of the senses, casting aside attraction and aversion. Such a person relishes solitude, eats lightly, controls body, mind, and speech, is ever engaged in meditation, and practices dispassion. Free from egotism, violence, arrogance, desire, possessiveness of property, and selfishness, such a person, situated in tranquility, is fit for union with Brahman (i.e., realization of the Absolute Truth as Brahman)”. Here, Shree Krishna explains the qualities and practices necessary for attaining Brahman-realization, the highest state of spiritual perfection. To achieve this, one must cultivate a purified intellect rooted in transcendental knowledge and maintain a controlled mind, free from attachments to likes and dislikes. The senses, body, and speech must be disciplined, and basic bodily needs like eating and sleeping should be balanced. A perfected yogi seeks solitude for deep contemplation, dissolves the ego, and transcends desires for power and prestige. By constantly focusing the mind on transcendence, the yogi becomes tranquil, free from desire, anger, and greed, and ultimately realizes the Absolute Truth as Brahman.

Description - This image explains the three goals of Hindu life to attain moksha.

Source - <https://weddingaffair.co.in/three-aims-life-dharma-artha-kama/>

Different schools of Indian Philosophy interpret moksha differently leading to ultimates as the attainment of supreme knowledge, to an unchanging, eternal state of existence. According to Advaita Vedanta, moksha is the realization of the non-duality (*advaita*) between the self (*atman*) and the ultimate reality (*Brahman*). In contrast, Dvaita Vedanta views moksha as eternal service to a personal deity, such as Vishnu or Shiva.

Prioritizing *Moksha* in socio-cultural analysis allows us to understand living experiences of Indian masses that embrace a multidimensional understanding of success, one that integrates material life with spiritual purpose. Many Western historians and philosophers have often misinterpreted and distorted this perspective, attributing India's perceived socio-economic lag to its philosophical emphasis on spiritual pursuits over material accumulation. However, it is essential to critically examine this Eurocentric narrative, which prioritizes the relentless pursuit of wealth and material success. Such an approach essentially diverges from the Indian philosophical framework, where excessive attachment to material possessions is tied to distraction from the ultimate goal—*moksha*.

When Hegel interpreted moksha as “annihilation”²⁴, this reflects a limited understanding of Indian spirituality (Hegel, 2001). Hegel's framework is deeply Eurocentric, positioning Western philosophy and Christianity as the pinnacle of spiritual and historical development. His dismissal of Indian thought as “dreamlike” and “imaginative” ignores its profound philosophical depth and practical relevance. By claiming that India is “outside of world history,” Hegel denies the agency of Indian civilization in shaping global history. This overlooks India's contributions to mathematics, science, literature, and philosophy, as well as its influence on other cultures through trade and cultural exchange.

Similarly, when Marx characterizes religion as opium for the masses, he neglects the broader concept of Dharma, one's duty assigned directly by the divine to fulfill (Sekhsaria,2020). He sees the spiritual pursuits of Indians, including the quest for moksha, as a reflection of their material conditions — essentially, as a form of “opium” that distracts them from addressing social and economic inequalities. Marx failed to recognize moksha as a legitimate and aspirational goal that coexists with material life. His interpretation reduced Indian spirituality to a byproduct of economic conditions, ignoring its intrinsic value and cultural significance.

Gandhi's day-to-day practice revealed a life deeply rooted in the principles of self-purification, self-discipline, and renunciation of material and bodily desires reflecting an actual pursuit of Moksha.

²⁴ “Part 1: The Oriental World” of G.W.F Hegel's *The Philosophy of History*.

His spiritual ideology was influenced by Advaita Vedanta,²⁵ Jain asceticism²⁶, and Gita, where moksha is not merely an abstract metaphysical concept but an achievable state through selfless service, non-violence (ahimsa), and complete detachment from worldly possessions.

George Orwell misunderstood the nature of Gandhi's thought, reducing it to a form of extreme asceticism that negated human experience rather than elevating it. Orwell's critique of Gandhi suggests an inherent skepticism about the legitimacy of his spiritual claims, as seen in the assertion that "Saints should always be judged guilty until they are proved innocent" (Orwell, 1949). The great Western author views Gandhi's renunciatory practices, such as his strict dietary discipline and vow of celibacy, as evidence of an "anti-humanist tendency" rather than a path to self-realization (reunification of atman with Brahman). Orwell asserts that Gandhi's philosophy "cannot be squared with the belief that Man is the measure of all things, and that our job is to make life worth living on this earth, which is the only earth we have." Indeed, it cannot: Gandhi's philosophy, which reflects Indian civilization, cannot be squared with Orwell's beliefs, which reflect Western civilization rooted in monotheism. Orwell's interpretation is fundamentally blind to Gandhi's conception of moksha, which was not an escape from worldly suffering but an ethical and moral commitment to social transformation through self-discipline and non-attachment.

Gandhi's understanding of moksha was inseparable from his political activism. His ideal of liberation was not limited to the personal realm but extended to the collective emancipation of society from colonial oppression, social injustices, and moral degeneration, which prevented the ultimate liberation in moksha. He believed in "sarvodaya" (the welfare of all) and saw individual self-purification as a means to uplift humanity (Prasad, 1960). His famous assertion, "The best way to find yourself is to lose yourself in the service of others," reflects his view that true liberation arises from selfless action rather than withdrawal from the world. Orwell, however, interprets Gandhi's asceticism as a retreat from the material world rather than an active engagement with it.

²⁵ Advaita Vedanta is a non-dualistic school of Hindu philosophy that asserts the ultimate reality (*Brahman*) as singular, formless, and beyond all distinctions. Rooted in the Upanishads, it was systematized by the 8th-century philosopher *Adi Shankaracharya*. According to Advaita Vedanta, the apparent multiplicity of the world is an illusion (*maya*), and the individual self (*atman*) is not separate from *Brahman*, but rather identical to it. Liberation (*moksha*) is attained through self-realization, where one transcends ignorance (*avidya*) and recognizes this fundamental unity. The philosophy emphasizes *jnana yoga* (the path of knowledge) as the means to enlightenment, advocating detachment from material existence and the dissolution of ego to realize one's true nature.

²⁶ Jain asceticism is a rigorous spiritual discipline rooted in the principles of non-violence (*ahimsa*), non-attachment (*aparigraha*), and self-discipline (*tapas*), aimed at achieving liberation (*moksha*). In Jain philosophy, the material world is seen as a source of bondage due to karma, and asceticism serves as the means to purify the soul and break free from the cycle of birth and rebirth (*samsara*).

Orwell's interpretation also fails to appreciate the centrality of detachment (*vairagya*) in Gandhi's worldview. Detachment, in Gandhi's philosophy, was not indifference to human suffering but a means to transcend selfish desires and act with moral clarity. As Gandhi himself stated, "The renunciation of the fruits of action is the center around which devotion, knowledge, and the desire for liberation revolve" (Gandhi, *Bhagavad Gita According to Gandhi*). Orwell misreads this detachment as a rejection of earthly concerns rather than a method of achieving true freedom from egoistic impulses.

Orwell's perspective reflects a Eurocentric skepticism toward a spiritual tradition fundamentally different from his own. He suggests that Gandhi's lifestyle was impractical in a "backward, starving, overpopulated country" and dismisses his advocacy of "soul forces" as medievalist. Unlike Orwell's materialistic worldview, which emphasizes the improvement of external conditions, Gandhi's approach suggests that true freedom begins with self-discipline and moral fortitude of the individual soul, which is a part separated from the whole, the universal soul of Brahman. Orwell's misunderstanding of Gandhi's concept of *moksha* lies in his inability to reconcile spiritual liberation with political engagement. He assumes that Gandhi's pursuit of purity and detachment must necessarily lead to a rejection of worldly responsibilities, whereas for Gandhi, these very principles were the foundation of his activism. Gandhi's *moksha* was not a passive withdrawal from the world but an active engagement with it, rooted in the belief that "the best politics is right action" (Mukherjee, 2010). Orwell's civilizational framework, with its clear categories and the separation of material and spiritual realities, prevents him from appreciating the depth of Gandhi's ethical philosophy, reducing it to unrealistic asceticism rather than recognizing it as a transformative force for both personal and societal liberation.

5. An Indic Mind: Contradictions are Complementary

The above discussion stresses the distinctions in how different mindsets perceive reality, even when things appear superficially similar. It reveals that the cultural and civilizational context in which a mind develops fundamentally shapes how we think, what we think, and the neural conditioning that ultimately differentiates us from one another. As Greenfeld (2025) observes, in Indic traditions, values like *satya* (सत्य) and *Nyaya* (न्याय), often translated as "truth" and "justice", are sometimes mistakenly equated due to historical misinterpretations. Unlike monotheistic frameworks that emphasize strict logical consistency, the Indic worldview does not view contradictions as inherently problematic. Instead, it embraces a more fluid understanding of reality, where the human mind is not limited to logical reasoning alone but is also guided by symbols, metaphors, and mythological narratives. Historical texts such as the Upanishads, the *Bhagavad Gita*, and the *Ramayana* seamlessly weave together logic, mythology, and symbolism, creating a worldview where contradictions are not seen as illogical but as complementary aspects of a greater whole.

This is evident in the paradoxical nature of Hindu deities and cosmic events, where opposites — such as creation and destruction, or life and death — are understood as interconnected and harmonious rather than conflicting.

Indic interpretation of the term Nyāya is right or justice. Etymologically this word means ‘that by which man is guided’ (nīyate aneneti nyāyah). “Nyāyaśāstra is therefore the science of right judgement or true reasoning”. The term *Nyaya* (न्याय) derives from the Sanskrit root words *ni* (down, back) and *eti* (he goes), suggesting a movement toward an original model or a return to a fundamental principle. According to the *Sanskrit to English Dictionary*,²⁷ *Nyaya* encompasses a wide range of meanings, including method, rule, system, justice, law, propriety, and logical reasoning. It signifies a structured approach to understanding and resolving questions of truth, morality, and governance. As a school of philosophy, *Nyaya* is one of the six orthodox (*āstika*) schools of Hindu thought, founded by the sage Gautama (also known as Akṣapāda). The *Nyaya* school is renowned for its emphasis on logic, epistemology, and the systematic analysis of knowledge. Its foundational text, the *Nyāya Sūtras*, attributed to Gautama and composed between the 6th century BCE and the 2nd century CE, outlines methodologies for acquiring valid knowledge (*pramāṇa*) and distinguishing it from invalid knowledge. Thus, *Nyaya* as a philosophy is not merely a concept but a comprehensive framework that integrates logic, justice, and ethical conduct. It serves as a guiding principle for rational inquiry, moral behaviour, and the pursuit of truth, making it an essential component of both philosophical discourse and practical life. Its etymological roots and philosophical depth highlight its enduring relevance as a system that leads individuals and societies toward correctness, fairness, and enlightenment. But in discussing this it is of paramount importance to keep in mind that every central term we employ — method, rule, system, justice, law, propriety, and logical reasoning, as well as truth and valid knowledge — for an Indian mind means something entirely different from what it means to a Western mind.

To further understand nyaya in lived realities, it is essential to first comprehend injustice and how to address it. People often recognize the meaning of justice through personal experiences of injustice, as history repeatedly demonstrates. For instance, Mahatma Gandhi's pursuit of justice and independence began when he personally faced humiliation and injustice. Injustice, therefore, serves as a powerful tool for understanding the value of justice. When individuals witness or experience injustice, they empathize with others who suffer similarly and become motivated to prevent such wrongs. Justice is thus an active, decision-making process aimed at correcting injustices and preventing their recurrence.

²⁷ www.wisdomlib.org. (n.d.). *Nyaya, Nyāya: 28 definitions*.
<https://www.wisdomlib.org/definition/nyaya>

Similarly, the concept of Satya in Indic philosophy is often confined to the ultimate reality of Brahman, the Supreme Consciousness that pervades all existence. Little emphasis is placed on the notion of falsehood, as nothing can truly be "false" in an absolute sense. Since everything emanates from and belongs to Brahman, the idea of falsehood is replaced by the concepts of illusion (Maya) and distraction. What may appear as false or unreal is often a result of ignorance or a distorted perception of reality, rather than an independent existence of falsehood. This understanding reinforces the idea that all existence, in its myriad forms, is an expression of the one, indivisible reality.

In a more poetic way, one can say, to understand the Indic mind is to step into a river where opposing currents merge into a single flow. A mind develops as per Indian norms, does not consider contradictions as problems to solve but truths to embrace — where light and shadow, creation and destruction, self and other, are threads in the same cosmic tapestry. Rooted in ancient wisdom yet vibrantly alive today, this worldview invites us to see paradox not as confusion, but as clarity.

When we speak of an Indic mind, we are referring to a vantage point where everything is perceived as interconnected, reflecting a sense of universal oneness, very different from the profound Western dualism. Even the duality of *Dvaita* (dualism) is not rejected but harmonized, like two notes in a raga, distinct yet creating a single melody. In Vedanta, *Advaita* (non-duality) dissolves the illusion of separation: the same Brahman pulses in the saint and the sinner, the mountain and the ant. The Upanishads whisper: "*Neti, neti*" (not this, not that), urging seekers to transcend binary labels. It emphasizes the process of negation in realizing ultimate reality (Brahman), teaching that Brahman is above all descriptions and traits, helping seekers to understand the unfathomable nature of existence.

A civilization can only be understood from within. This does not mean that one must be a native to be capable of a valid interpretation. Rather, one must begin, as Greenfeld's essay suggests, from the recognition that civilizations fundamentally differ from one another and the study of a particular civilization's first principles. Everything else, for as long as it exists, is embedded in them and follows from them, starting from the language in which they were originally codified and including their concepts, values, institutions, the ways its members think, feel, and act.

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